

THE GRAMMATICAL CATEGORY OF NUMBER AND ITS FUNCTIONS

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ABSTRACT

It is certainly vital for communicating in any languages, humans are in need of all parts of speech, though one of the most indispensable parts is noun. Nouns are the most numerous class of words. This article is devoted to give information about the grammatical category of number and its functions.

Key words: nouns, numbers, category, quantitative, common noun, proper noun, geographical names, countable nouns, prefixes, suffixes.

Number forms in all languages are more closely connected to nouns for the semantic character of a specific category of words since the category of number represents the quantitative relationships between objects. The grammatical category number is used to represent items with quantitative features. Grammatical number is one of the manifestations of a more general linguistic category of quantity, along with lexical manifestation (lexical number), which can take the shape of a number or cardinal designations in other parts of speech (such as many, singular, and other).

Number is strange as a separate grammatical category because it is essentially a noun. The language type determines the various ways to express a number. We shall attempt to distribute the studied language's names and nouns with -simple suffixes do not have prefixes or suffixes. They are indestructible: chair "chair", table "table", and so on. There are derived elements (prefixes, suffixes, or both) in -derived nouns: in+experi+ence "inexperience", read+er "reader" -derived nouns have derived elements (prefixes or suffixes or both): read+er "reader", in+experi+ence "inexperience";

Compound nouns are built from two or more bases:

snow + ball "snowball", black + bird "thrush", *dancing-girl* "dancer and others.

There are two categories for nouns: proper names and common nouns.

In Arabic, this divergence is more obvious. Proper names are distinctive labels given to distinctive people or things. Proper names be human names (e.g., Mary "Mary"), geographical names (e.g., London "London"), month and day of the week names (e.g., February "February"), ship, hotel, or club names , and so on, depending on their significance. While still common nouns, a large number of nouns simultaneously evolved into proper names (Snow "Snow - snow"). Languages often experience the opposite effect, when proper names become common nouns (Jack "Jack" - jack "guy" and others).

Common nouns are names that can be applied to any member of a certain group of people.

There are different classes of common nouns:

- class nouns;
- collective nouns;
- real nouns;
- ABSTRACTnouns.

Nouns can also be categorized based on other cues: those that signify countable objects are countable nouns, and those that signify uncountable objects are uncountable named nouns.

Quantitative relationships are, therefore, the content of the category of numbers as they are reflected in human cognition and linguistic forms. The primary and significant function category of numbers, according to S.D. Katsnelson, is "quantitative actualization, the goal of which is the restriction of the virtual concept expressed by the name with using grammatical means." [1]. Considering this, E.Kh. Khabibullina says that quantitative updating cannot underlie the category of number, if only because the grammatical plural meaning connected with quantitative uncertainty (any more than one), quantitative certainty is more naturally reflected with the help of the numeral, but not with numerical form. [2]. One cannot but agree with S.D. Katsnelson that "when a name appears in a speech, the meaning of a name the common noun needs to be limited and the numbers expressed by the category distinctions of singleness - multiplicity (duality, trinity or paucity) contribute to the fulfillment of this task" [1]. Indeed, singular form, duality, trinity and spideriness update, limit the meaning of the name, the meaning of the plural, indefinitely. More Alexandrian grammarians (ancient grammarians) called singular - certain, and pi. - indefinite. Hence, "The lexicogrammatical category of number expresses quantitative relationships that exist in reality, reflected in consciousness of native speakers of a given language and having a morphological expression in the corresponding forms of the given language" [3].

The purposes of grammatical number are far from exhausted in terms of expressing quantitative relationships between objects and processes in reality. The

number category is multifunctional. Not only are names countable things included in the domain grammatical forms of number, but also designations of internumeral concepts: collectivity, materiality, and ABSTRACTness.

Furthermore, there are differing opinions on whether a number should be classified as a lexico-grammatical category or a grammatical category. As a result, E.F. Safina believes it is "more appropriate to qualify the number as a grammatical category rather than a lexico-grammatical category, because the lexical grammatical category is distinguished by such linguistic meaning" for which there are no specific regular ways of expression. All nouns have numerical forms, so far as the number is concerned [8]. According to her, "grammatical inflectional category" is what number is. In line with E.Kh.Khabibulina the number of names nouns is not only a lexical and grammatical category, but also a category with great stylistic expressiveness" [2]. We share this viewpoint. The internal concepts—collectivity and materiality—are what it is.

As mentioned above, in many languages the category of number is mostly binary on the paradigmatic axis (singular - plural), but in a number of languages it has more than two members: the dual number is added (for example: Classical Greek, Sanskrit, Arabic) - it is used with reference to two objects, sometimes a triple number (for example, some Papuan and Malanesian languages - it is used with reference to three plural of a small amount. In some languages have special forms for plural collective, for multiple distributive (not just "tables", but each of the "tables"), for quantified multiplicity and others. According to the outstanding American linguist J. Greenberg [4], "no language can have a trinity without having a plural number" ("No language has a trial without having a plural") [5]. Similar implicative universal arranged in a hierarchy of numbers. So, the languages of the world are different from each other by what numerical characteristics of names are expressed using special indicators.

In English, for example, if the number of objects identified by the name is greater than or equal to two, the name must contain a plural indicator. In Arabic, the number of objects designated as plurals must be more than two. Some languages, such as Arabic, need specific markers if the names express a pair of objects. In this scenario, the so-called dual number is used, which is found in several Semitic and Austronesian languages. Finally, there is a variant of the word that signifies a collection of a modest number of objects (from three to five).

Such a number is known as paucal (from the Latin word paucus, which means "small"); it appears in Arabic and a number of Oceanian languages. The Hierarchy of Numbers establishes implicit dependencies between the presence of the aforementioned numbers in the world's languages: there is a paucal number in the language y, a binary number in the language y, and a plural in the language. This hierarchy is obviously identical to the following universal implicative system: There

is a paucal number in the language. There is a binary number in the language. There are plurals in the language.

Does this imply that the entire range of number types is only a subdivision of the plural, as some linguists believe?

This issue requires careful consideration plurality in these languages.

Number forms have different meanings. Yes, Linguistic encyclopedia [6] distinguishes three semantic types for singular:

1.singularity (basic value);

2.commonality;

3.out-of-pair in number - singularia tantum, real and ABSTRACTnames; a special group in the sphere of grammatical singularity is formed by collective names.

In English language there exists Five different semantic types For Pluralization:

1. a distributive set; 2. a collective set; 3. discrete plural (fundamental value);

4.Representative set - A gathering of people gathered at the request of one of their representatives. This kind is also connected to the so-called approximate set (e.g., the 1980s); 5.plural of greatness, politeness (Russian polite form you); for instance, English, the Browns - Browns, spouses, and family. Compared to other languages, English has the most restrictive category of numbers; it is a feature of the name noun. Thus, there are two types of numbers in English: singular and plural. The following system oppositions between singular and plural nouns were developed by the renowned linguist J. Buranov:

1. The contrast between marked and unmarked plural forms.

2. The contrast between singular marked forms and singular marked forms

3. Opposing the use of unmarked single and plural forms. [7]

The primary method of opposition for solitary forms and pi is 1. In English language names are nouns. Non-marking of the singular forms are defined as the absence of a unique indicator of unity, or zero exponent, as in the examples boy "boy" and book "book" of English. The primary morpheme of English can be identified as plural. In contrast to the singular's zero sign, -s/-es is used instead.

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